

CONCLUSIONS

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This conference was evidently an experimental conference. The amount of new information is very large, the data are very interesting and very stimulating.

I. ψ - PARTICLES

The most impressive for me are the results on new particles, the ψ 's. We now definitely know that there are two narrow states, the first one having a width of ~ 70 keV and the second one, the ψ' , a width of ~ 200 keV. There is a broad enhancement at 4/GeV and there is a plateau above 4 GeV with a ratio R of hadronic to muonic cross section equal to 6. To the left of the enhancement this ratio is equal to 2,5.

Thus the main effects are established: two narrow resonances, one broad structure and the step at 4 GeV. The nature of all these effects is far from being clear at present. The large $R=6$ is believed to be due to new constituents of the hadrons. But where are other manifestations of these constituents? There is no change in K spectra which we expected at the step at 4 GeV, there is no discontinuity in the multiplicity

of charged decay products in e^+e^- annihilation and there are no two and three-body peaks in the Dalitz plots which were shown to us by Feldman. These were the most popular predictions of the models with charm half a year ago and none of them is substantiated. There is a great mystery: 40 % of the ψ' decay goes to channels which are not yet identified and it is quite unclear what is the nature of these channels. But there is also a great hope in this new particle region, and that are the 20 μe coincidences found at SLAC at 4.8 GeV among approximately 10,000 events, reported here by Feldman. If these μe -events exist, the most natural interpretation is that they are a manifestation of charmed particles, namely of the vector mesons F^x, \bar{F}^x , decaying into pairs $\mu\nu$ and $e\nu$.

II. SEARCH FOR CHARM

This subject is closely related to the first one. There are indications for some unusual phenomenon which appears in various processes, and which in our jargon is called charm. May be there are many various phenomena in reality. First of all I will mention the very high, unexpectedly high ratio of direct lepton production to pion production which in several high energy hadron-hadron collision experiments is of the order of 10^{-4} . This is much higher than the ratio predicted by the decay mechanisms of the known particles. Next, there is one $\Delta Q = -\Delta S$ BNL event, which is interpreted as the decay of a charmed particle. This is an event in neutrino collision. This decay corresponds to a very high portion of the proton-neutrino cross section, but the FNAL-Michigan results which were presented at this conference by Nezzrick do not substantiate such a large cross section. Indeed, these results indicate that if $\Delta Q = \Delta S$ is violated in neutrino reactions, then the cross section is perhaps at least two order of magnitude less than that which can be deduced from the single event of the BNL experiment. In fact, no $\Delta Q = -\Delta S$ events were found so far at FNAL. There is one

candidate at Gargamelle which was presented here by Bertrand-Coremans, and it has been found in a sample of 6000 events, which is again a very small portion. I have talked with many people here, and still it is not clear to me whether this is a candidate or a real event with $\Delta Q = -\Delta S$.

Another possible manifestation of production of new particles are the dimuons. There were three different talks on this subject. One from the Harvard-Pensylvania-Wisconsin-Fermilab /HPWF/ collaboration, given by Reeder, who presented about 60 dimuon events which were produced in neutrino collisions. Sciulli reported on the ~ 10 events found at Batavia by the Caltech group, and Vovenko told us about a negative result /0 event/ at Serpuchov. In the discussion it was stressed by Rubbia that the energy at Serpuchov is too low for producing dimuons. It is not clear to me whether there is or there is not contradiction between these experiments. But I was told by the authors that in a period which may be less than one year we shall have new results which hopefully will clarify the situation.

I would like to point out that at first sight it seems to me that the results obtained by SLAC on μe and by FNAL on $\mu\mu$ may not correspond to the same phenomenon. This is because if you produce in a neutrino experiment an F^* , then, as was emphasized here by Gershtein, the process will be of diffractive type.

The neutrino, which will appear in the decay of the F^x will obtain a large part of the total energy. But we have seen here that at least in several such events there is practically no invisible energy. Thus this is perhaps a point to work on it further.

There is also a persistent search for charm in other types of experiments which were not presented here. There is a series of papers which report on search for charmed particles in proton-proton or proton-nucleus collisions, especially in cosmic rays. There is a preprint by an Indian group, which registered in gold mines deep underground 4 or 5 events, looking like decays of new particles. There are several papers by Japanese physicists working with nuclear emulsion who report on strange events with creation and subsequent decay of unknown particles with a lifetime $\sim 10^{-13}$ sec - just that expected for charmed decays. The first such paper by Niu et al appeared several years ago. Recently they published several new events some of them obtained in Batavia with the same emulsion technics. Two weeks ago, just before we left for this conference, a group at the Lebedev Institute published in JETP Letters two unusual emulsion events.

The situation now is a very peculiar one. In a sense charm is overdiscovered. And yet it is my personal feeling and it is the general feeling that the existing evidence is still too shaky.

The charmed particles are overpredicted. They were invented many years ago and they are desperately needed for theoretical reasons. Of course the prediction of charmed particles is not of such a pure mathematical nature as e.g. the prediction of the positron by Dirac, and is not so straightforward as the prediction of the neutrino by Pauli just from energy conservation. But if we compare it to

the prediction of the muonic neutrino in the late fifties, then it seems to me that charmed particles have more ground to exist, are more basically expected, than muonic neutrinos. You remember that in 59 Pontecorvo proposed a ν - experiment to look for ν_{μ} . Now, at this conference, he discussed a new experiment of the "beam dump" type to look for neutrinos produced in the decay of charmed particles. Such experiments will be done in many laboratories in the near future. I will not speak here about other experiments aimed to discover new particles.

It seems to me quite sure that long before the next Balaton meeting there will be a demographical explosion in the world of elementary particles, and there will be a new large family, or several new families of particles added to the known ones. The reason for this belief is that it is based on the same theory which has so successfully predicted the neutral currents.

III. NEUTRAL CURRENTS

Neutral currents which are so young were not at all considered as exotic objects at this conference. They are treated on the same footing as the charged currents, but with somewhat less statistics. They were first discovered in Gargamelle, and now we have here some beautiful results from several groups: Gargamelle, Batavia, Argonne. We were told by Sciulli that the neutral currents possibly represent some mixture of V and A, but these results are very preliminary and will be improved in the near future. Rubbia told me about the preparation of a $\nu_{\mu}p \rightarrow \nu_{\mu}p$ experiment, which is a good way to ascertain the type of the interaction.

The situation with other neutral currents is not so advanced as with the interaction of the ν_{μ} with nucleons. Reines told us about the continuation of his work on $\nu_e e^-$ -scattering at the reactor. There are approximately 200

candidates with \sim six hundred background events; with time the ratio signal-to-background improves steadily, there is continuous progress and we may hope for more definite results. A project has been presented here by Chen of an experiment on the meson factory at Los Alamos /LAMPF/ which would give 600 events of $\nu_e e$ -scattering with only a 10 % background. Unfortunately the experiment is scheduled to be done only at the end of this decade. $3 \pm 0,5$ events of $\nu_\mu e$ -scattering have been presented here by the Gargamelle group, and a new experiment by the Aachen-Padova group is under way.

There is quite a new field, which is opening. We have heard here the talk by Bouchiat on the weak neutral currents ($\bar{e}e$) ($\bar{N}N$). These are parity violating currents, which must lead to some new phenomena in atomic physics due to the mixture of atomic states with opposite parities. This brings us some new possibilities because it refers to branches of physics where precision is extremely high, it refers to optics; experiments with lasers are now done and preliminary studies at several laboratories are carried out. I am sure there will be a very interesting development. Serious efforts are still needed to make these experiments feasible, but people working in this field are very optimistic.

The ($\bar{\mu}\mu$) ($\bar{N}N$) neutral currents were discussed here by Jarlskog, Fiorini, and Backenstoss. There are two possibilities to measure these currents. One is the study of parity violating effects in μ -atoms, the other - to carry out high energy μN - scattering experiments. Both of them are very difficult experiments, and it is not clear to me which one has more chance of being successful, perhaps the second one is somewhat better.

($\bar{N}N$) ($\bar{N}N$) experiments has been discussed here by Fiorini who pointed out that the result by Lobashov in measuring the circular polarization of the photon in the process $np \rightarrow d\gamma$ is approximately by 2 orders of magnitude higher

than that expected according to a simple theory with charged currents. Thus Fiorini thought that the effect may be due to neutral currents. But we had here a talk by Nagle on a 15 MeV (pp)(pp) experiment with polarized beam with parity violation effect $(1 \pm 4) \cdot 10^{-7}$ which is in no contradiction with the simple-minded calculation with charged currents only. Perhaps it is not easy to reconcile these two experiments and we should wait for further development.

IV. $\nu_{\mu}\mu$ CHARGED CURRENTS

The data are very numerous and there is a crude agreement with the expectations of the parton model:

- 1./ There is a linear rise of the cross section with energy.
- 2./ There is a crude scaling.
- 3./ Strange particles are copiously produced by charged currents above 10 GeV /FNAL - Michigan/.

However, there are some deviations:

- 1./ There is a violation of charge symmetry, reported by the HPWF-group. The region $x \ll 1$; $y \ll 1$ corresponds to the forward scattering of the leptons. Therefore the total energy-momentum transfer to the nucleon is small and in this region the ratio $\nu:\bar{\nu}$ should be 1:1, and in the experiment it is 3:1. This is very bad for the theory, it contradicts fundamental things; not just the parton model, but the type of the interaction, the type of the Lagrangian is at stake, and I can't see how this result can be reconciled with what we know about the weak interaction. There was a lobby discussion between Rubbia, Sciulli and Zacharov in the hall of the hotel Annabella which lasted four hours, and the conclusion is that we should wait for new experimental results.

- ii./ There is a possible violation of scaling in $\bar{\nu}$ -experiments above 30 GeV, but I shall not comment on this.

V. OTHER EXPERIMENTS

I'll mention briefly some other experiments which were presented at this conference. A result of the measurement of the electric dipole moment of the neutron has been presented by Ramsey: $d = (0,4 \pm 1,1) \cdot 10^{-24}$ e x cm which is the lowest experimental value we know. A high precision experimental value for muon lifetime was given by Zinov /Dubna/. There are experiments, partly done, on the improvement of the conservation of baryonic and leptonic charge described here by Reines and Fiorini, and an experiment in Dubna on the conservation of muonic charge, mentioned yesterday by Pontecorvo.

There is also an experiment on strong interaction at BNL carried out by the group which discovered the J-particle and reported here by Chen. They have found an interesting new phenomenon in the inclusive spectra of pairs $K^+\pi^-$, $K^+\pi^-$, etc. The spectra of 9 such pairs form three groups and show some similarities inside these groups. This result was not adequately digested at this conference, it belongs to strong interaction physics and I will not discuss it here.

VI. THE SUN AND THE STARS

There is a very interesting progress in new detectors for the neutrinos from the Sun and from stars /Lande, Pomansky, Zatsepin/. The Gallium-Germanium detector is studied now with the aim of detecting the main part of the neutrino flux coming from the Sun /low energy neutrinos/. There is also the new neutrino detector which will be used by Lande to study the birth of the Super-novae.

VII. THEORY

The situation with the theory at this conference was different from that with the experiment. The presentation of the various fields was somewhat fragmentary, and we had here some samples of various approaches, of various trends, and of various models: phenomenology, partons, quarks, gluons, bags, strings, symmetries, supersymmetry. I will not review these papers, just because of lack of time, and anyway it would be a hard work to speak and to listen. I'll make only a few remarks on some problems and models which were discussed.

The first remark is that perhaps the easiest explanation of what we see in the experiments designed for the search of charmed particles would be offered by some models with a larger number of quarks, and in particular by models containing 6×3 coloured quarks. Such models may explain some of the puzzles we have in this field. But of course these models look pretty ugly, and from an aesthetic point of view they are not very attractive. And therefore many theoreticians, and I would say almost all the experimentalists do not believe in these models. The criterion of beauty is a very strong one, and may be it is the only one. But a new idea, which is just born, may look like an "ugly little swan". There is a fairy tale by Andersen, I don't know its english title...

Ramsey: "Ugly duckling, maybe a swan..."

O: I see. So this is maybe the situation with these 18 coloured ducklings...

I would like to add some more remarks on quarks which were discussed here by Filippov, Kunszt, Nanopoulos, Tadič, Zacharov and Zeldovich. When we went on the excursion to Badacsony, one of the prominent experimentalists asked me how could I give a talk on quarks and gluons, - particles which nobody have seen and perhaps nobody will see in the future?

The reason for not only speaking about, but even working with these particles is that quark models have very large predictive power. Many hadrons have been predicted on the basis of quark models like η , η' , Ω and so on, long before they have been found experimentally. A number of important symmetries have been found due to quark models and many selection rules were postulated in this way. These rules have been tested by experimentalists in a period of almost 20 years and they are alive. This predictive power is the main reason in this case; if something works, you should work with it.

One of the most interesting developments of the recent years is the possibility to calculate the strong interactions at small distances which appears in the models with gluons. Asymptotic freedom means that the strong interaction decreases when we go inside the hadrons and so it is not only possible to calculate the diagrams in lowest order perturbation theory but to sum up large classes of diagrams and to get very interesting results.

Another field of high interest are classical objects. They were considered here by Kuti, Patkos and Zeldovich. We have heard about condensate, solitons, strings, monopoles, bubbles. In a recent publication in JETP Letters Shapiro proposed a hypothesis, according to which the stability of the ψ -meson is of such classical nature, ψ being something like a quasistable soliton, a bubble of hadronic condensate. There is a number of objections to such point of view. But if charm interpretation of ψ 's will fail, we would be forced to explore this approach further.

There is a deep interrelation between elementary particle physics and the whole body of physics. For many years solid state physics profited from the development in elementary particle physics. The technics of Feynman graphs was used with great success in solid state physics. Now solid state

physics pays its debts to elementary particle physics, especially to high energy physics, and such notions as phase transition, spontaneous violation, domains come into our consideration in elementary particle physics. This is very promising. This is the manifestation of the trend to unification of various physical regions and various approaches.

In particular the process of unification is very intensive for the interactions of the elementary particles. The whole history of elementary particle physics which began with the discoveries of β , α and γ -rays is a manifestation of the interrelation, interinfluence of strong (α), weak (β) and electromagnetic (γ) interactions. But it seems that now this interdependence goes over into a unification, into fusion. These interactions are now much closer to each other than ever before, and we are at the eve of the synthesis of various types of interactions.

There is also a deep connection between cosmology and astrophysics on the one hand, and elementary particle physics on the other hand. As demonstrated here by Zeldovich, we can use our knowledge in cosmology to test various Lagrangians, various models of elementary particle physics, and to discard some of them. This is again a manifestation of unity in physics. In a sense the neutrino may be considered as a symbol of this unity. Neutrino penetrates many problems and strongly interacts with these problems. I think you all agree with me that this interaction very much increased during this v75 week at the Balaton. And we are all thankful for this to the Hungarian Academy of Sciences, to the Hungarian Physical Society, to Professor Marx to our colleagues here and friends, and I would like to say them thank you, спасибо, köszönöm szépen.